

Wood use and forest management at the Late Bronze Age copper mining site of Priggwitz-Gasteil in the Eastern Alps – A combined anthracological, archaeological, and palynological approach

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ABSTRACT

The Late Bronze Age mining site of Priggwitz-Gasteil provides a wealth of sources of information for the reconstruction of wood use, past vegetation, and forest management at a copper production facility. In this paper we have combined charcoal analyses from domestic and workshop contexts and the investigation of mining timbers found in the backfill of the opencast copper ore mine with the first results from pollen analyses from the nearby Saubachgraben mire. The complementary information from these different contexts allowed a reconstruction of the impact of settlement and mining activities on the natural mixed forest around the site, chiefly composed of beech, spruce, and fir. Forest clearing affected mainly spruce. Despite the dominance of spruce among the conifers, however, fir wood was exclusively selected for the production of mining timbers, which were used to support the opencast mine walls or for water management constructions. The gathering of firewood for domestic hearths followed the principle of least effort, leading to a secondary succession with pioneering species in the immediate surroundings of the mining settlement. The investigated wood and charcoal finds indicated an intentional and selective use of the locally available wood species. At the current state of the investigations, there is no evidence of scarcity or shortage in the wood supply.

1. Introduction

1.1. State of research

Up to the period of industrialisation, all past mining and metal working activities were in constant need of energy in the form of wood fuel, and they also relied on a supply of construction timber. Wood with particular properties was used for the construction of the mine workings, including the timbering of the shafts and adits and constructions for accessing the mines (ladders, staircases), extraction, and ventilation; the production of tools and implements (picks, hammers, buckets, shovels etc.); the construction of ore processing plants (e.g., sluice boxes); the lighting of the mines (not only underground mines); and the

construction of shelters, dwellings and other buildings next to the mine. Wood was also needed in large quantities as the only source of energy for the smelting of ores, as well as for heating and cooking for the miners (Boenke, 2015, Grabner, et al., 2014, Grabner, et al., 2015, Oeggl and Schwarz, 2015, Thomas, 2018).

The investigation of past vegetation, the reconstruction of wood use and forest management, and the study of the environmental impact of mining are therefore crucial for our understanding of past mining organization. In archaeological contexts, only a tiny proportion of the wood used for mining purposes has survived, depending mainly on human selection and the preservation conditions. From a methodological point of view, it is therefore desirable to combine as many data sources from as many contexts as possible in order to develop a valid

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Table 1

Prehistoric mining sites in the Eastern Alps, overview of published data on wood use and vegetation history. Table: uibk/P. Trebsche, K. Oeggl, OeAW-OeAI/A. G. Heiss.

No.	Mining area (state, country)	Pollen archives	Mining timbers, wooden artefacts	Charcoal analyses
1	Oberhalbstein Valley (Grisons, CH)	Barscheinz near Bivio (Stockmaier, forthcoming)	(Oberhänsli, et al., 2019, Reitmaier-Naef, et al., 2020)	(Isler, forthcoming, Oberhänsli, et al., 2019, Reitmaier-Naef, et al., 2020)
2	Trentino, IT	none	(Silvestri, et al., 2015)	(Silvestri, et al., 2015)
3	South Tyrol, IT	none	none	none
4	East Tyrol (Tyrol, AT)	none	none	none
5	Schwaz-Brixlegg area (Tyrol, AT)	Frauensee near Kramsach (Walde, 1999); Koglmoos in Schwaz (Breitenlechner, et al., 2010); Oberkienberg near Brixlegg (Walde, 1999); Schwarzenbergmoos near Radfeld (Schibler, et al., 2011)	(Goldenberg, 2013, Nicolussi, et al., 2010, Staudt, et al., 2019)	(Heiss, 2001, Heiss and Oeggl, 2008, Nicolussi and Pichler, 2013, Pichler, et al., 2013, Schibler, et al., 2011)
6	Kitzbühel-Kelchalm-Jochberg (Tyrol, AT)	Rauber at Kelchalpe (Viehweider and Oeggl, 2013, Viehweider, et al., 2015)	(Pichler, et al., 2009, Pittioni and Preuschen, 1947, Preuschen and Pittioni, 1937, Preuschen and Pittioni, 1954)	none
7	Saalfelden Basin	none	none	none
8	St. Veit-Klinglberg (Salzburg, AT)	Haidberg-Götschenberg (Wahlmüller, 1988, Wahlmüller, 1992)	none	(Gale, 1995)
9	Mitterberg (Salzburg, AT)	Bürgelhöhe (Wahlmüller, 1992); Kreuzbergmoos (Breitenlechner, et al., 2014); Sulzbachmoos (Stöllner, et al., 2011); Wilder See (Stöllner, et al., 2011)	Arthurstollen, Hauptgang (Thomas, 2018); Troiboden (Pichler, et al., 2018, Stöllner, et al., 2010, Stöllner, 2019)	none
10	Eisenerzer Ramsau (Styria, AT)	Leopoldsteiner See (Drescher-Schneider, 2003, Drescher-Schneider, 2004, Klemm, et al., 2005)	none	only for medieval and modern period (Klemm, et al., 2005)
11	Prigglitz (Lower Austria, AT)	Saubachgraben (current study)	current study	current study
12	Hallstatt (Upper Austria, AT)	Siegmoos (Festi, et al., 2021, Knierzinger, et al., 2021)	(Grabner, et al., 2009, Grabner, et al., 2014, Grabner, et al., 2015)	none
13	Dürrenberg (Salzburg, AT)	Moor bei Neuhäusel; Moor bei Ruhrkapelle (Oeggl, unpubl. data)	(Boenke, 2002, Boenke, 2005, Boenke, 2015, Boenke,	none

Table 1 (continued)

No.	Mining area (state, country)	Pollen archives	Mining timbers, wooden artefacts	Charcoal analyses
			2020, Lobisser, 2005, Lobisser, 2015, Lobisser, 2017, Stöllner, 2002, Stöllner, 1999)	

reconstruction of wood use patterns. Ideally, on-site or near-site pollen archives provide information about the past vegetation thus allowing a much more detailed interpretation of preserved wooden artefacts and charcoals (Breitenlechner, et al., 2010, Breitenlechner, et al., 2014, Heiss and Oeggl, 2008).

Despite intensified research into wood use in prehistoric mining during the past ca. 20 years, there are still very few prehistoric mines in the Eastern Alps where all three categories of source material (pollen, wood, and charcoal) have been analysed (Table 1). Broadening this database is therefore a major research desideratum to better understand the economic and technological aspects and a prerequisite for possible future comparative studies of wood use in prehistoric mining.

1.2. Methodological background

1.2.1. Pollen analysis

Analysis of the temporal changes in the pollen composition of peat deposits in former mining areas can be used to reconstruct the dynamics of past vegetation over time. Specific indicator pollen of settlement activity and agriculture from ruderal (e.g., ribwort, *Plantago lanceolata*) and cultivated plants (Cerealia-type and rye, *Secale cereale*) render the influence of humans on vegetation visible (Behre and Kučan, 1986, Breitenlechner, et al., 2014). Other micro-fossils of a pollen profile, such as micro-charcoal, often in combination with macroscopic charcoal, can provide direct information about the burning of firewood or deforestation events (Breitenlechner, et al., 2013, Carcaillet and Thion, 1996). Various studies confirm that macro-charcoals from smelting fires, kilns and cooking hearths at archaeological ore-processing sites are representative of the contemporary local vegetation (Engel, 1993, Heiss and Oeggl, 2008, Knapp, et al., 2015, Ludemann, 1996, Ludemann and Nelle, 2002, Nelle, et al., 2013, Py, et al., 2014).

1.2.2. Wood and charcoal remains

A direct approach to reconstructing prehistoric wood use is, of course, feasible if wooden artefacts are preserved. The use of different wood species, of different age classes and diameters, or of different growth types for specific purposes tells us a lot about the knowledge of craftsmen and the availability of wood. The wet, salty, or dry conditions in some prehistoric mines and their associated workplaces often provided good chances for the preservation of wood. However, thorough reconstruction of local and regional vegetation is required as the basis for an assessment of wood choices and for the identification of imported wood species. This reconstruction must be based on independent data sources such as pollen archives or accumulations of randomly preserved wooden remains (such as charcoal from soil flotation samples) because the wooden artefacts themselves may be biased by human selection and thus can only provide vague indications of the surrounding woody vegetation.

Anthracology, the analysis of charcoals from archaeological contexts, has proven to be an efficient tool for the investigation of wood-fuel selection and/or the composition of the vegetation surrounding a site

Fig. 1. Map of the Eastern Alps with prehistoric mining regions, numbers corresponding with Table 1. Red areas: copper mining, blue areas: salt mining. Map: OeAW-OeAI/A. G. Heiss (after Heiss, et al., 2021, based on Stöllner, 2009).

(Dufraisse, 2008, Kabukcu and Chabal, 2021, Kreuz, 1992, Ludemann and Nelle, 2002, Théry-Parisot, et al., 2010, among others). Where possible, charcoal analysis is combined with pollen analysis for vegetation reconstructions, since it can show species that are underrepresented in or absent from pollen assemblages, such as poplar/aspens (genus *Populus*), whose pollen decays in a short time after dispersal (Campbell, 1999), and insect-pollinated trees and shrubs, such as maple (genus *Acer*) and elder (genus *Sambucus*) (Nelle and Bankus, 2002).

In many cases, however, charcoal is the only tool for woody vegetation reconstruction, especially in dry soils without pollen or (uncharred) wood preservation. It is therefore crucial to analyse charcoal assemblages that accumulated as a result of long-term activities (Kabukcu and Chabal, 2021, Théry-Parisot, et al., 2010).

2. The Late Bronze Age copper production site of Prigglitz-Gasteil

The site of Prigglitz-Gasteil is located at an altitude of ca. 700–730 m a. s. l. on the eastern slope of the Gahns mountain in the municipality of Prigglitz, Neunkirchen district, Lower Austria (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). In the 1950 s, a Late Bronze Age copper-producing site was discovered and first excavated by archaeologist Franz Hampl and mineralogist Robert Mayrhofer (Hampl and Mayrhofer, 1963). After a long break, excavations were resumed from 2010 to 2014, followed by geophysical surveys and core-drilling prospecting in 2017 and 2018 (Trebsche and Pucher, 2013, Trebsche, 2015a, Trebsche, 2015b).

The site represents a ca. 3 ha large Late Bronze Age mining camp or settlement where chalcocite was mined, beneficiated, smelted, and

processed into bronze products. The copper production facility can be characterized as a regional centre of copper production and bronze casting based on the evidence of an openwork copper ore mine and nearby bronze casting workshops (Haubner, et al., 2017, Haubner, et al., 2019, Mödlinger and Trebsche, 2021, Mödlinger, et al., 2021). The copper ore mine was in operation from ca. 1050 BCE to 780 BCE. As a result of the mentioned prospecting, it was possible to reconstruct an open-pit copper-ore mine of the Late Bronze Age, that developed in three phases (Pit A, B and C) and reached a maximum depth of 33 m below the present surface (Trebsche/Schlögel/Flores-Orozco, submitted). The drilling cores provided evidence that the mining process was interrupted by a mining subsidence event, that can be dated shortly after ca. 920 BCE (Trebsche and Weixelberger, 2022).

As opposed to the other Bronze Age copper mines in the Eastern Alps, the Prigglitz opencast mine is directly associated with a settlement area and bronze workshops. In the immediate vicinity of the copper-ore mine, prehistoric miners established dwellings and workshops on top of the mining dumps after having them levelled as horizontal terraces for building purposes. Two of the terrain terraces (T3 and T4) were excavated from 2010 to 2014. These excavations brought to light mining-related activities, like butchering, cooking and food consumption, production of tools from animal bones and antler as well as the remains of casting workshops for the manufacture of bronze products (Trebsche and Pucher, 2013, Trebsche, 2015a, 2015b).

Within the framework of an ongoing, multi-disciplinary research project, archaeometallurgical (Haubner, et al., 2017, Haubner, et al., 2019, Mödlinger and Trebsche, 2021, Mödlinger, et al., 2021), archaeozoological (Trebsche and Pucher, 2013), archaeobotanical (Heiss,

Fig. 2. Prigglitz-Gasteil, plan of the site with sampling locations. Orthophoto © Federal Government of Lower Austria, with kind permission. Map: uibk/P. Trebsche.

et al., 2021), and geoarchaeological investigations (Trebsche and Weixelberger, 2022) have already provided detailed evidence of aspects of everyday life and work at Prigglitz-Gasteil during the Late Bronze Age.

2.1. Local environment

2.1.1. Local geology and soil chemistry

The site is located in the foothills at the extreme south-east of the Gahns mountain. The Gahns is a plateau-like spur of the Schneeberg, the highest mountain (2076 m a. s. l.) in the Austrian federal state of Lower Austria, whose massif is part of the Rax-Schneeberg group. While the high plateau of the Gahns consists of Mesozoic dolomites and limestones, the foothills to the east and south are part of the older Palaeozoic greywacke zone, formed of metamorphosed sedimentary rocks (Scheffczik, 1978).

Soils such as eutric cambisols (Pehamberger and Gerzabek, 2009) and rendzina on weathered limestone are prevalent in the Gahns area to the west of the mining site, whereas a pattern of alternating eutric and dystric cambisol soils is found to the east. The soils in the vicinity of the copper mine are therefore generally rich in humus, but also rather shallow and prone to rapid drying-out. Gleysol soils occur along the edge of Saubachgraben mire, about 500 m to the east (BFW, 2021).

2.1.2. Climate

In terms of climate, the site of Prigglitz-Gasteil is situated in a transitional sub-Illyrian zone between the subatlantic climate of the Eastern Alps and the subcontinental climate of the Pannonian Basin (Bobek, et al., 1971). However, the orographic influence of the Alps in the Eastern Alpine foothills means that winds often blow from the west, north, and south-east, frequently reaching high speeds. These winds can intensify evaporation and cause severe drying-out, despite annual precipitation rates of up to 500 mm/yr. Cold, warm, and dry phases alternate rapidly in individual areas of the Eastern Alpine foothills,

depending on the interplay of these influences (Popovtschak, et al., 2021).

The Late Bronze Age in central Europe coincides with the latest phase of the Subboreal climatic period, a warm-dry phase with only slight fluctuations in mean temperatures and precipitation rates (see, for example, Jahns, 2000). During the 8th century BCE, however, mean temperatures decrease accompanied by an increase in precipitation. These changes are commonly associated with the abandonment of the lakeside settlements in Switzerland and southern Germany (Popovtschak, et al., 2021, Rösch, 2013, Schibler, et al., 1997). The later phases of mining activity at Prigglitz-Gasteil may at least have been influenced by these climatic changes.

2.1.3. Vegetation

Today's landscape around the Prigglitz-Gasteil site consists mainly of arable fields, cultivated grassland, and commercial forestry (Kohler-Schneider and Heiss, 2015, unpublished data). The latter can be attributed to the fact that the soils mentioned in section 2.1.1 above are often of medium to poor agricultural value and are therefore rather being exploited for wood.

The model of potential natural vegetation (PNV, see Tüxen, 1956) characterizes the area as a transitional zone between montane fir-beech forests and submontane oak-beech forests (Wagner, 1971).

Current forest stands at altitudes of between 350 and 600 m a. s. l. and 600–800 m a. s. l. are sessile oak-common hornbeam forests (*Galio sylvatici-Carpinetum* and *Carici pilosae-Carpinetum*) mixed with beech (*Fagus sylvatica*). Beech forests occur with sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*), common ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) and sycamore maple (*Acer pseudoplatanus*). To the west, the high, wooded Gahns plateau (1,200 m a. s. l. on average) is dominated by spruce (*Picea abies*) and larch (*Larix decidua*). Deciduous tree species such as beech and sycamore maple appear only sporadically. However, their occurrence is probably restricted by commercial forest management (Scheffczik, 1978).

At altitudes comparable to the site of Prigglitz-Gasteil, spruce-fir-

Fig. 3. Prigglitz-Gasteil. Aerial view from the mining site (at the bottom) towards the Saubachgraben mire (in the centre foreground). The location of the pollen profile is indicated. View towards east. Photo: Crazy Eye/R. Weßling.

beech forests can be found in the wider area, as well as two forms of black pine forests (*Euphorbio saxatilis-Pinetum nigrae* and *Seslerio-Pinetum nigrae*) which merge into forests with Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) in the form of *Erico-Pinetum sylvestris* further to the west. Scots pine also occurs south of the site, mixed with oak (*Deschampsio flexuosae-Quercetum*) and intermixed in fir-beech forests (Kilian, et al., 1994).

Black pine (*Pinus nigra*), here represented by the Austrian black pine (*Pinus nigra* subsp. *nigra* var. *austriaca*), has its northernmost distribution in the eastern Alpine foothills and is considered a character species of the region. While most of the modern populations of *Pinus nigra* in the area derive from 18th century CE plantations for resin extraction, an estimated 10–20 % of the black pine forests at the Eastern Alpine margin are natural populations growing on sunny slopes and shallow carbonate and dolomitic soils (Zukrigl, 1973, Zukrigl, 1999). Again, Prigglitz-Gasteil is in a marginal situation, generally allowing for the growth of *P. nigra* (see the discussion in section 5.1).

2.2. Research goals

It is unique for Prigglitz-Gasteil that a mining site with the complete production chain and associated dwellings was unearthed. Moreover, the good preservation of organic materials enables the reconstruction of the supply chains of a mining site for the first time. In this paper, we focus on the wood supply and present new data from recent excavations and core drillings at the Late Bronze Age copper mining site of Prigglitz-Gasteil in Lower Austria. The site yielded preserved mining timbers and timber artefacts from mine contexts, it was systematically sampled for charcoal remains from domestic contexts and workshops immediately next to the opencast copper mine, and it provided an appropriate pollen archive in the nearby Saubachgraben mire.

Based on these three categories of finds we discuss the following questions regarding past vegetation and land use: What was the vegetation like around the mining site of Prigglitz during Late Bronze Age? Did mining activities impact on the composition of the forest? How was the wood used? Was there a selective use of certain tree species or specific wood qualities? Before going into detail, we want to briefly underline the importance of a combined approach, using different

sources, for the reconstruction of past forest exploitation and wood use.

3. Material and methods

3.1. Terminology, nomenclature, and systematics

Classification of mining timbers follows the terminology of Volmer and Zimmermann (2012). Plant taxonomy follows Fischer, et al. (2008), while species attribution to phytosociological class groups is based on Oberdorfer, et al. (2001), as well as differentiation between climax/indifferent and pioneering woody taxa: Hazel (*Corylus avellana*), poplar/aspens (*Populus* sp.) and willow (*Salix* sp.) were considered as pioneering taxa, together with elder (*Sambucus* sp.), which mainly grow on forest clearings and debris. The term “climax vegetation” is used in the sense of “zonal vegetation group” (Leuschner and Ellenberg, 2017). All charcoal and wood identification data were recorded and evaluated using the database ArboDat (Kreuz and Schäfer, 2004, Recker, et al., 2016), which also incorporates the phytosociological work by Oberdorfer, et al. (2001).

3.2. Palynological analyses

3.2.1. Field work

In 2018 and 2019, extensive prospectations in the vicinity of the archaeological excavations of Prigglitz-Gasteil were conducted to locate suitable peat deposits for this study. Specific criteria were thickness and undisturbed bedding. Finally, the mire at Saubachgraben (47°42'47.34" N, 15°56'42.06" E; 635 m a. s. l.) was selected because of its immediate vicinity to the ore deposits and the mining site and its large size of approximately 0.4 ha (Fig. 3). Mires of this size collect a local and extra-local pollen signal (Jacobson and Bradshaw, 1981), which carries the best palynological information about anthropogenic interference with vegetation. The 1.9 m thick peat core was extracted as a monolith with a Geonor piston corer (5.2 cm diameter) in the summer of 2019. It was then stored in a cold room at a constant temperature of 6 °C and protected from sunlight until subsampling for pollen analysis.

Table 2

The ten flotation samples, from each of which 100 charcoal fragments were taken for examination and analysis, classified into three chronological units of mining activity (right). Table: uibk/P. Trebsche, OeAW-OeAI/T. Jakobitsch.

Archaeological phase	Stratigraphical unit	Find no.	Absolute dating (simplified)	Chronological unit
T3-08 D	413	681	1045/1015–1000/975 BCE	1045/1015–1000/975 BCE
T3-08 E	714	1114	1045/1015–1000/975 BCE	
T3-10	8	42	920–915 BCE	920–900 BCE
T4-09	43	193	900 BCE	
T4-11	1218	2421	905 BCE	
T4-13 A–G	88	289	920–910 BCE	
T4-13 B	1023	2107	910 BCE	
T4-13 F	1058	2150	920–910 BCE	
T3-08 A	800	1302	825–810 BCE	850–810 BCE
T3-08 B	827	1431	850 BCE	

3.2.2. Lab work

First, the core was subsampled to produce test specimens of constant volumes (1 cm³) taken at intervals of 10 cm. The sample intervals were then subsequently reduced to 5 and 2.5 cm to achieve a higher time resolution for the chronological units relevant for this study. Tablets with a defined amount of exotic pollen of common clubmoss (*Lycopodium clavatum*) were added before the chemical treatment (Stockmarr, 1971) to allow calculations of pollen concentrations. Chemical digestion of the samples for palynological analyses followed Erdtman (1960). Microscope slides were then prepared, embedded in glycerine, and stained with fuchsin.

The pollen analysis was conducted under a transmitted light microscope at 400x magnification (and in critical cases at 1,000x magnification). About 500 arboreal pollen (AP) grains were counted in almost every sample to generate a robust dataset. Pollen and spore identification was conducted using standard identification keys (Beug, 2004, Fægri and Iversen, 1993, Punt, 1976, Punt and Clarke, 1980, Punt and Clarke, 1981, Punt and Clarke, 1984, Punt, et al., 1988) and the modern pollen reference collection at the Department of Botany, University of Innsbruck.

In addition to pollen and spores, micro-charcoal particles (*particulae carbonae* of size classes < 50 µm and > 100 µm) were also counted. The pollen counts are represented as percentage diagrams, the basic calculation sum is composed of arboreal (AP) and non-arboreal pollen (NAP), excluding the Cichoriaceae (Asteraceae-Cichorioideae) and Cyperaceae pollen as well as spores. Micro-charcoals are also exempted from the basic calculation sum and are displayed as percentage values of the pollen sum defined above.

3.2.3. Dating

The chronology of the core was obtained by radiocarbon dating of seven peat samples (Accelerator Mass Spectrometry, AMS), carried out by the Poznań Radiocarbon Laboratory, Poland. First, three samples were taken to date the lowermost organic layer (depth 195–197 cm), the first peak in charcoal particles (depth 134.5 cm) and the first appearance of *Secale* pollen (depth 100 cm). Later, four more samples were taken in regular intervals from 90 to 60 cm depth to improve the depth-age-model for this section of the profile.

3.3. Charcoal analyses

3.3.1. Find context and preservation

The charcoal for analysis originated from the terrain terraces immediately next to the opencast mine where copper ore had been extracted. Ten sediment samples for flotation were taken from two excavation areas on terrain terraces T3 and T4. The sediments derived from the cultural layers, which are composed of debris that had

accumulated during the period of use of the miners' camp and workshops. As already mentioned in section 2.1, the two terrain terraces investigated provided evidence of mining-related activities, such as butchering, cooking, and food consumption, as well as working of animal bones and antlers. Casting workshops for the manufacture of bronze products were also attested in both excavation areas. The archaeobotanical samples were thus associated with both domestic and workshop contexts in the miners' camp and they represent a mixture of all mentioned activities, rather than being attributable to specific individual activities. For details of the global sampling strategy and for the evaluation of botanical macro-remains, see Heiss et al. (2021). It is important to mention that the charcoal analyses are not related to the primary smelting of copper ores, the most fuel consuming activity at the site, because the smelting furnaces have not yet been discovered and excavated.

Hundred charcoal pieces (>2 mm) per sample were randomly selected from each of the ten soil samples, resulting in a total of 1,000 fragments for analysis. These charcoals were not dated directly in order to avoid the old wood effect (Waterbolk, 1971). Instead, the dating of the charcoal samples follows the relative chronology based on site stratigraphy and the evaluation of 32 radiocarbon dates measured for short-lived organic samples (animal bones and charred plant remains other than charcoal). As the discussion of the radiocarbon calibration model goes far beyond the scope of this paper, the results are here only presented in a summarized form in Table 2 for all archaeological phases providing charcoal samples.

For the study of diachronic trends in this paper, the samples were grouped into three chronological units. The first unit corresponds with the first period of opencast mining (ca. 1045/1015 to 1000/975 BCE), the second one represents samples from the period immediately after the mining subsidence event (shortly after 920 BCE), and the third unit includes samples from the latest phase of mining operations at Priggwitz-Gasteil (850–810 BCE). For a detailed discussion of the absolute chronology, see Trebsche and Weixelberger (2022).

3.3.2. Identification

Species identification was carried out using an Olympus BX53M metallurgical microscope with a magnification range of 50x to 500x, assisted by standard identification literature (e. g., Schweingruber, 1978, Schweingruber, 1990) and an interactive identification key (Heiss, 2000–2009). For further details of wood-anatomical literature used in this project, see also Section 3.4.2. Although the weights of the charcoal fragments were recorded, only their numbers were used for the evaluation of taxon proportions, since outcomes are usually very similar for both measures (Badal-García, 1992, Chabal, 1997, Dufraisse, 2008).

In charcoal analysis, estimating the original mean diameter of the wood can be helpful for investigating a possible selection of wood for

Table 3

Radiocarbon data for the Saubachgraben mire profile. Table: uibk/K. Oegg. Data from Poznań Radiocarbon Laboratory, calibrated using OxCal 4.4 (Bronk Ramsey, 2009, Bronk Ramsey, 2021) and the IntCal 20 calibration curve (Reimer, et al., 2020).

Lab no.	Sample no.	Depth [cm]	Material	Radiocarbon age	Calibrated date (1 σ ; 68.3 %)	Calibrated date (2 σ ; 95.4 %)
Poz-137881	SBG-0600	60	peat	715 \pm 30	1271–1298 CE	1333–1386 CE
Poz-137818	SBG-0700	70	peat	655 \pm 30	1291–1388 CE	1280–1395 CE
Poz-137819	SBG-0800	80	peat	780 \pm 30	1229–1274 CE	1219–1280 CE
Poz-137820	SBG-0900	90	peat	895 \pm 30	1052–1213 CE	1043–1220 CE
Poz-131027	SBG-1000	100	peat	2390 \pm 30	BCE 513–401	BCE 725–394
Poz-131028	SBG-1345	134.5	peat	2805 \pm 30	BCE 1000–921	BCE 1047–845
Poz-120465	SBG-1960	195–197	peat	7010 \pm 40	BCE 5978–5842	BCE 5988–5788

thickness (Dufraisse, et al., 2020, Ludemann and Nelle, 2002, Ludemann, 2008). Therefore, minimum diameters were estimated from the charcoal fragments by using a diameter stencil (Ludemann and Nelle, 2002). Mean diameters of some charcoal fragments could not be estimated due to their bad state of preservation. By fitting the growth ring curvature and the angle of the wood rays into the stencil, it was possible to classify the charcoal pieces into five diameter classes. The mean diameter (mD) of each tree species was then calculated using the following formula: $mD = [n(0-2\text{ cm}) * 1 + n(2-3\text{ cm}) * 2.5 + n(3-5\text{ cm}) * 4 + n(5-10\text{ cm}) * 7.5 + n(>10\text{ cm}) * 15] / n$ (Ludemann and Nelle, 2002, Ludemann, 2008).

3.4. Mining timbers

3.4.1. Find context and preservation

Mining timbers were discovered during core drilling conducted in 2017 from the top of the mining heaps covering the copper ore mine (see Fig. 2). The objective of the coring was to clarify the thickness of the mining heaps and the depth of the workings. Core KB01 revealed dump layers from mining activities that were kept moist by groundwater or slope water. A total of 17 timbers were preserved in this environment, embedded in the sediments at depths of approximately 20.5 to 29.5 m. Twenty sediment samples were also taken from the moist layers at depths of between 20.8 and 31.75 m and checked for pollen preservation. Unfortunately, these results were negative.

The stratification documented in the cores provided evidence of a Late Bronze Age opencast mine, which reached a depth of up to 32 m below the present ground surface. The open pit was completely back-filled by waste rock-pile material, as well as material from a landslide resulting from the aforementioned mining subsidence event around 920 BCE (Trebsche and Weixelberger, 2022).

Although the substance of the timbers was well preserved throughout, most timbers were severed by the drill (18 cm in diameter), resulting in mechanical deformation and partial fraying at the cut edges. All the timbers were packed in their moist condition and stored in a cool place, protected from light, from the time they were found until the dendrochronological analysis, and then freeze-dried for permanent preservation. Material adhering to the surfaces was intentionally left to allow further micromorphological or microbiological examination.

3.4.2. Identification

For precise species identification, the recognition of microscopic features is necessary. These features (e.g., presence or absence of resin canals, spiral thickening of tracheids or vessels, etc.) are well described for almost all the wood species in question (Bosshard, 1982, Grosser, 1977, Sachsse, 1984, Schweingruber, 1990, Wagenführ, 1999) and can usually be detected with the help of micro-sections. The timber fragments were primarily identified from smooth-ground cross-sections under a reflected-light microscope.

3.4.3. Dating

Dendrochronological analyses of the timbers were carried out at the Institute of Wood Technology and Renewable Materials at the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU) in 2017

(Grabner, 2017). In the case of eleven samples, tree-ring sequences ranging from 4 to 45 years could be measured. Absolute dendrochronological dating, however, was not successful. Therefore, two or three radiocarbon samples were taken from each of the five timbers with the most growth rings. These samples were measured at the Poznań Radiocarbon Laboratory (PL) using the Accelerated Mass Spectrometry method and calibrated by wiggle matching (Bronk Ramsey, et al., 2001) using the OxCal 4.4 software (Bronk Ramsey, 2009, Bronk Ramsey, 2021) and the IntCal 20 calibration curve (Reimer, et al., 2020).

3.4.4. Classification

Since only relatively short sections of the worked timbers were preserved, their classification was based primarily on comparable finds from other prehistoric mines in the Eastern Alps. Larger ensembles of wood finds were published from the Bronze Age underground mines of Mitterberg (Thomas, 2018), the Bronze Age processing plants of Mitterberg (Pichler, et al., 2018, Stöllner, et al., 2010, Stöllner, 2019) and the Kelchalm near Kitzbühel (Pichler, et al., 2009), the Bronze Age mine workings of Hallstatt (Grabner, et al., 2009, Grabner, et al., 2014, Grabner, et al., 2015), the Late Bronze Age and Early Iron Age fire-set pits in the Schwaz-Brixlegg area (Nicolussi and Pichler, 2013, Pichler, et al., 2013), the Iron Age underground mine at Dürrnberg near Hallein, and the contemporaneous industrial settlement in Ramsautal (Boenke, 2002, Boenke, 2005, Boenke, 2015, Boenke, 2020, Lobisser, 2005, Lobisser, 2015, Lobisser, 2017). For classifying the pit timbers from Priggltz-Gasteil, the categorization devised by Peter Thomas (2018) for the pit timbers from Mitterberg was particularly suitable. Basically, he distinguishes between log roundwood (RH-S, German abbreviation of *Rundholz Stamm*), round branch wood (RH-A = *Rundholz Ast*), radially split logs (SH-R = *Spaltholz radial*) and tangentially split logs (SH-T = *Spaltholz tangential*).

4. Results

4.1. Pollen analyses: First insights into the local vegetation history

The available palynological studies provide preliminary results in a coarse temporal resolution but reflect the fundamentals of the local vegetation development. The palynological pilot study has already provided at least a rough outline of the development of the local vegetation. In total, seven radiocarbon samples provided the basic data for calculating the depth-age relationship and the variability of peat accumulation in the Saubachgraben mire (Table 3, see also Suppl. Fig. 1 and Suppl. Fig. 2; for a detailed sediment description see Suppl. Table 1). Organic deposition started in the 6th mill. BCE. In the following five millennia, peat development was very poor, amounting to about 40 cm in total, which corresponds to an accumulation rate of 0.08 mm/yr. This means that one pollen sample represents about 125 years. During the Late Bronze Age, conditions for peat formation became more favourable and about 0.8 mm/year was deposited for about 400 years. In this section of the peat column, the time resolution per sample corresponds to about 12 years. Then hydrological conditions changed, and peat formation was reduced again to about 0.07 mm/yr for the next 1500 years. From the High Medieval period onwards, the growth rate of the mire

Fig. 4. Relative pollen diagram of the Saubachgraben mire peat sequences. From left to right: depth scale (time-linear plot), radiocarbon data (uncalibrated BP), calendar years (calibrated BCE/CE), cultural periods, main diagram (in black): ▲ = beech (Fagus), ● = pine (Pinus), Δ = spruce (Picea), solid black line = sum of woody species, curves highlighted in green = percentage diagrams of woody species, curves highlighted in light green = grasses (Poaceae), olive green = sum of anthropogenic indicators, curves highlighted in light green = anthropogenic indicators, red curves = crops, curves highlighted in light green = herbs, mosses, and ferns, black highlighted = micro-charcoal, curves not highlighted = permille values. Diagram: uibk/K. Oegg.

Table 4

Overview of all identified wood types in the analysed charcoal assemblages from Priggwitz-Gasteil (N = 1,000) by number of fragments and their weight. Relative and absolute frequencies are given in Fig. 5. Table: OeAW-OeAI/T. Jakobitsch.

Chronological unit	T3-08 D		T3-08 E		T3-10		T4-09		T4-11		T4-13 A-G		T4-13 B		T4-13 F		T3-08 A		T3-08 B			
	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]
Stratigraphic unit	413		714		8		43		1218		88		1023		1058		800		827			
Find no.	681		1114		42		193		2421		289		2107		2150		1302		1431			Total
	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]	n	[g]
Climax and indifferent taxa																						
<i>Abies</i>	3	0.71	17	2.16	21	5.94	6	0.19	-	-	12	1.35	12	1.45	20	0.38	7	0.04	2	0.01	100	12.23
<i>Acer campestre</i>	-	-	-	-	2	1.15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	0.04	1	0.02	6	1.21
<i>Acer platanoides / A. pseudoplatanus</i>	-	-	1	0.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.03	1	0.02	-	-	3	0.14
<i>Carpinus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.04	1	0.04
<i>Fagus</i>	67	29.68	15	1.97	2	0.36	5	0.22	18	0.50	77	6.84	30	2.26	71	2.69	22	0.43	8	0.17	315	45.12
<i>Fraxinus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.06
<i>Larix / Picea</i>	-	-	2	0.47	1	0.30	5	0.52	12	0.20	-	-	6	0.57	-	-	-	-	2	0.04	28	2.10
<i>Pinus type sylvestris</i>	-	-	41	6.65	73	22.85	45	6.00	2	0.08	2	0.12	1	0.04	7	0.28	4	0.13	15	0.26	190	36.41
<i>Quercus</i>	2	0.12	12	1.71	-	-	31	2.07	1	0.01	-	-	49	1.59	-	-	15	0.20	5	0.08	115	5.78
<i>Sorbus / Cotoneaster</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0.08
<i>Taxus</i>	-	-	1	0.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.64	-	-	1	0.01	-	-	3	0.83
Pioneering taxa																						
<i>Betula</i>	-	-	1	0.08	-	-	-	-	3	0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	0.13
<i>Corylus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.02	-	-	1	0.02
<i>Populus</i>	-	-	-	-	1	0.29	-	-	25	0.56	-	-	-	-	-	-	17	0.75	2	0.10	45	1.70
<i>Populus / Salix</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	36	0.96	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	0.13	30	0.64	76	1.73
<i>Salix</i>	28	1.84	9	1.32	-	-	2	0.10	2	0.09	-	-	-	-	-	-	6	0.01	27	0.50	74	3.86
<i>Sambucus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.01	1	0.02	2	0.03
Other																						
indet. charcoal	-	-	1	0.38	-	-	3	0.62	-	-	6	1.78	1	0.1	-	-	12	0.42	5	0.15	28	3.45
indet. outer bark	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.01	3	0.23	-	-	1	0.05	-	-	1	0.02	6	0.31
Total	100	32.35	100	15.01	100	30.89	100	9.86	100	2.46	100	10.32	100	3.43	100	3.43	100	2.21	100	2.05	1.000	115.23

was higher, about 1.1 mm/yr on average, which corresponds to a roughly decadal time resolution of the sampling for the youngest parts of the peat sequence. The resulting relative pollen diagram is illustrated in Fig. 4.

The earliest pollen deposits in the Saubachgraben mire profile was dated to the Neolithic (Fig. 4). During that period the mire was surrounded by beech (*Fagus*) and, on shallow ground, by pine (*Pinus*) forests. At altitudes below the mire (submontane belt), oak (*Quercus*) flourished alongside the beech, whereas in regions above the mire (montane belt), *Fagus* was associated with spruce (*Picea*) and fir (*Abies*). Alder (*Alnus*) grew alongside rivulets and at the foot of damp slopes. Forests seem to have been dense since both the frequency and diversity of pollen from herbal taxa were low for this period.

The first changes in the composition of the forests occurred in the Early Bronze Age. At that period, spruce and larch (*Larix*) spread at higher altitudes, while fir, oak, beech and lime (*Tilia*) became less important in the areas around the mire. Wider openings in the forest cover were not observable from the pollen values for herbs, but willow (*Salix*) proliferated. Along with these changes, the first cereal grains were also observed at a depth of 142.5 cm, suggesting farming in the wider vicinity of the mire. Unfortunately, this first appearance of cereal pollen can only be dated by interpolation between the 5th and 1st mill. BCE (interpolated absolute date: ca. 1800 BCE) and consequently cannot be pinpointed with certainty. For this section of the pollen profile, more radiocarbon dates are needed.

In the following period, beech and spruce declined, while pine

achieved a maximum around 1500 BCE (still roughly interpolated). The expansion of ferns (i.e., monolet spores), horsetails (*Equisetum*), and to a small extent sedges (Cyperaceae) indicates hydrological changes in the mire. Moreover, the subsequent spread of *Alnus*, *Fagus*, and *Picea* suggests more humid conditions in the study area. However, there was also a moderate increase in the amount of grass pollen, pointing to clearings in the forests in the mire's vicinity. This was accompanied by the occurrence of anthropogenic indicators (*Artemisia*, Chenopodiaceae = Amaranthaceae p. p.) and Cerealia-type pollen in the 11th c. BCE. The settlement activity continued until the 8th c. BCE. It was located in the montane belt, as shown by the decreasing values of pine and spruce, while beech and fir expanded, suggesting a regeneration of the submontane forests in the vicinity of the mire.

At the beginning of the Iron Age there were marked changes in deposition conditions, probably caused by changing water levels in the mire over a period of about 400 years. This is reflected by large fluctuations in the local tree curves, e.g., those of alder, beech, fir, oak, pine, and spruce. Their sequences of maxima and minima do not show any regularities which could have been suggestive of a secondary succession; e.g., the maxima of pioneering trees such as birch (*Betula*) do not correspond with minima of stand-forming trees (*Abies*, *Fagus*, *Quercus robur*-type, *Picea*, *Pinus*). Anthropogenic and cultural indicators are absent from this section of the pollen diagram, so that human interference can also be excluded.

It is only from the 5th c. BCE that Cerealia-type pollen and anthropogenic indicators are recorded in the pollen diagram again. These

Fig. 5. Proportions of identified woody taxa in the charcoal assemblages from the flotation samples taken at Prigglitz-Gasteil. Numbers in round brackets () – absolute taxon frequencies. N = 966. Illustration: OeAW-OeAI/T. Jakobitsch, A. G. Heiss.

farming activities occurred at the lower altitudes, as indicated by the decline of beech and oak. The low grass and herb values suggest that the clearing of the forest in the surroundings of the mire was moderate. This continued to be the case in Roman and Early Medieval times.

Massive interference in the forest vegetation took place during the High Medieval period. In the 11th c. CE, beech and oak were cleared. Alder, hazel, larch, and fir were also affected by logging. From then on, the mire was surrounded by grasslands and fields on which cereals – now including rye (*Secale*) to a large extent – were grown. Walnut (*Juglans regia*) was introduced and planted close to the farmhouses. The vegetation of the mire changed too. It became overgrown by sedges (Cyperaceae) and members of the composite family (Asteraceae-Cichorioideae).

The present vegetation conditions were shaped at the beginning of the modern period. In the study area, forests with beech, fir and oak disappeared, benefitting spruce. Pine (*Pinus*) expanded on shallow soils and on scree slopes, intermixed with isolated specimens of larch. Rye was no longer cultivated and cereal farming in general lost its importance, its place taken by the grassland farming of today.

4.2. Charcoal analyses

A total of 1,000 pieces of charcoal were analysed, 966 of which were identifiable to genus or species level (Table 4). Twenty-eight fragments remained entirely unidentified due to their bad preservation, while six fragments initially assessed as charcoal turned out as (indeterminate) fragments of outer bark.

Seventeen different taxa were identified. *Fagus sylvatica* is the best represented totalling to 33 % of the identifiable charcoal fragments and *Pinus type sylvestris* (cf. Chabal and Heinz, 2021) is the second one with 19 %. Light-demanding pioneering taxa such as *Populus* and *Salix* occur in considerable numbers (Fig. 5).

In Fig. 6, the occurrences of pioneering species in relation to climax and indifferent species are displayed according to chronological groups. The proportion of pioneering species is quite low in the first two chronological units (12–19 %), while in the third unit (from 850 until 810 BCE) the pioneering tree proportion (52 %) exceeds that of the climax and indifferent species (48 %).

Values for mean diameter (mD) calculations were obtained from 236 charcoal pieces. Others were not measurable due to their bad state of

Fig. 6. Proportional shifts from dominating climax and indifferent woody taxa (darker tones) towards pioneering taxa (lighter tones) at Priggglitz-Gasteil per chronological unit as defined in Table 2. N = 966. Illustration: OeAW-OeAI/T. Jakobitsch.

Table 5

Diameter classes and mean diameter (mD) measured from charcoal fragments from Priggglitz-Gasteil. N = 236. Table: OeAW-OeAI/T. Jakobitsch.

	Diameter classes					mD [cm]
	I (<2 cm)	II (2–3 cm)	III (3–5 cm)	IV (5–10 cm)	V (>10 cm)	
<i>Abies</i>	5	2	2	18	6	7.4
<i>Acer campestre</i>	2	1	–	–	–	1.5
<i>Acer platanoides</i> / <i>A. pseudoplatanus</i>	–	–	1	1	–	5.8
<i>Carpinus</i>	1	–	–	–	–	1.0
<i>Fagus</i>	47	17	20	4	–	2.3
<i>Larix</i> / <i>Picea</i>	5	2	1	1	1	3.7
<i>Pinus type sylvestris</i>	10	8	15	21	11	6.3
<i>Populus</i>	4	4	2	–	–	2.2
<i>Populus</i> / <i>Salix</i>	4	1	2	–	–	2.1
<i>Quercus</i>	–	2	4	5	1	6.1
<i>Salix</i>	2	–	–	1	–	3.2
<i>Taxus</i>	2	–	–	–	–	1.0
Total	82	37	47	51	19	

preservation. Four taxa (*Corylus*, *Fraxinus*, *Sambucus*, *Sorbus/Cotoneaster*), each with one find only, were not measurable for mD values. The largest number of charcoals (82) was observed in the smallest diameter class (0–2 cm), of which *Fagus sylvatica* accounted for 47 (Table 5). The mD value of the analysed beech wood is 2.3 cm, which is low in comparison to other taxa. Coniferous trees like *Abies alba* and *Pinus type sylvestris*, for example, reach higher values in the charcoal record (*Abies*: 7.4 cm; *Pinus*: 6.3 cm). Likewise, *Quercus* sp. wood has a higher value, at 6.1 cm.

4.3. Mining timbers

Among the Priggglitz finds were one round log (Timber 03), 13 split timbers, including four which had been radially split and eight which had been tangentially split (in the case of one piece, the method of splitting was not precisely determinable), as well as two lighting tapers (Timbers 04 and 17) and one wood chip (Timber 16) (Fig. 7, Table 6).

The split timbers from Priggglitz could be divided into two groups: a relatively homogeneous group of laths/boards/planks (with rectangular or elongated cross-sections) and an inhomogeneous group of split logs with different cross-sections (halved logs, slabs). Both groups included

examples of radial and tangential splitting. The first group included seven timbers (Timbers 05, 06, 11–15), for the production of which coniferous woods (as far as determinable fir) with diameters of at least 20 cm were used. The preserved growth rings (9–34) naturally indicated only the minimum age of the logs. The average growth ring width was 2.2 mm (1.4–3.0 mm). Thus, the logs split into laths, boards, and planks had grown much faster than the roundwood, no. 3.

The second group mentioned above, the split logs, included six finds. Of these, the radially split logs were mainly very thin conifers with a diameter of 5–7 cm (Timber 01, 02, 07). Thicker coniferous logs with diameters of over 10 cm were tangentially split, resulting in slabs with irregular cross-sections (Timber 08, 09, 10). In contrast to the stem logs and split planks/boards, four of the six timbers in this group still had their bark. The split logs in the second group had between 11 and 45 growth rings, which in all cases was only an indication of minimum age, as the inner parts of the log were missing. What they had in common, however, was a very small average growth ring width of well under 1 mm (0.4–0.8 mm); the only higher value, from Timber 10, was not representative, as it was measured at a branch attachment point. Thus, slow-growing conifers (fir, as far as determinable) were split radially in the case of thin stems (5–7 cm diameter) and tangentially in the case of thicker stems (10–20 cm diameter).

Of the 17 wood finds, ten were determined as fir (*Abies alba*), five others generally as coniferous, while two could not be determined due to the bad preservation of their wood anatomical features. The timbers dated from ca. 1030 BCE (Timber 14) to ca. 920 BCE (Timber 08), as summarised in Table 7. The dating results were fully published by Trebsche and Weixelberger (2022).

5. Discussion

5.1. Firewood

Indeed, all major woody taxa observed in the charcoal assemblage thrived in the vicinity of the archaeological site during Bronze Age; species composition reflects a forest vegetation similar to the modern natural vegetation on the eastern border of the Alps (Kilian, et al., 1994, Zukrigl, 1973, Zukrigl, 1999). Furthermore, the percentage curves of the pollen diagram display no shortfall of any of the major wood taxa recorded in the charcoal assemblages. This implies that no human selection criteria were applied to wood collection at the Bronze Age mining site; all accessible forest-tree species were used as firewood for domestic purposes and for bronze casting. Considering the “principle of least effort”, firewood was gathered within a limited area involving all accessible woody species without selection and in proportions similar to their occurrence in the environment (Prior and Price Williams, 1985, Shackleton and Prins, 1992, Théry-Parisot, et al., 2010).

The identification of the wood species gathered for domestic fires and bronze casting workshops allowed a partial reconstruction of the surrounding natural forests. For example, the charcoal samples indicated a high prevalence of *Pinus type sylvestris* wood. However, *Pinus sylvestris* and *P. nigra* cannot be differentiated by their wood anatomical features, and given the presence of natural black pine forest stands today (Kilian, et al., 1994, Zukrigl, 1973, Zukrigl, 1999), it is possible that, in addition to *P. sylvestris*, *Pinus nigra* was also amongst the trees used at the mining site. The high occurrence of both fir (*Abies alba*) and beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) indicates dense climax forest stands, since both taxa prefer shade (Oberdorfer, et al., 2001).

The chronological sequence of the samples as shown in Fig. 6 indicates a significant rise in the number of pioneering species (*Corylus avellana*, *Betula* sp., *Populus* and/or *Salix* sp., *Sambucus nigra* or *S. racemosa*) in the latest chronological unit (850–810 BCE). The pollen profile from Saubachgraben mire shows an overall low percentage of *Salix* pollen when compared to the occurrence of *Alnus* pollen. Therefore, it is indeed most likely that the *Populus/Salix* charcoal originated from openings in the local forests surrounding the copper production

Fig. 7. Classification of wood finds from core KB01 at Prigglitz-Gasteil, classified according to Thomas (2018). Rows 1 and 2 show the cross-sections orthogonal to the axis of the mining timbers. Orientations of the growth rings are schematized. Drawings: uibk/P. Trebsche.

facility rather than from nearby wetland sites.

In the earlier periods, 1045/1015–1000/975 BCE and 920–900 BCE, climax forest species and indifferent species had much higher proportions in the charcoal assemblage. This indicates that the constant need for firewood in the mining settlement influenced the forest. The human impact of the mining activities can be seen in the change of vegetation, which happened between the second chronological unit (920–900 BCE) and the last unit (850–810 BCE). Parts of the forest, probably in the vicinity of the working stations, had been cut down for wood and the newly created open soil gave pioneering species the opportunity to establish themselves. They were also promoted through the creation of debris heaps, on which only pioneering tree species could grow. The pioneering woody vegetation was then extensively used for firewood in the last chronological unit (850–810 BCE), leading to the high percentages of *Populus* and *Salix* among the recovered charcoal samples.

Taking the results from the diameter reconstructions carried out on the charcoal, it seems at least possible that trunks and thicker branches of beech trees were used for other purposes than as fuel, while only thinner branches could have been used for burning. However, due to the overall low amount of charcoal fragments large enough to allow diameter reconstruction, we know such conclusions cannot be made yet, given the available dataset. Mean diameter (mD) analysis was also, tentatively, conducted with respect to the chronological sequence of the analysed samples. The purpose was to test whether the diameters of wood changed over time due to selection or availability. At present, however, no significant trend is detectable and – more importantly – the data available for each chronological unit are clearly insufficient to allow reliable conclusions. Additional charcoal analyses should however allow insights into such changes, they are envisioned for a follow-up study.

5.2. Mining timber

Since the pit timbers found at Prigglitz were not in any recognizable construction context, their intended function can only be surmised. A starting point for consideration was provided by the proportions of timber elements used, with boards/planks accounting for 50 %, followed by other split timbers (43 %), with the only round log representing 7 %.

The high proportion of boards and planks among the Prigglitz finds is in contrast with mining timbers from underground mines in the Alpine area. For example, in the Arthurstollen mine at Mitterberg, 56 % were miscellaneous split timbers, followed by 22 % boards/planks, 19 % roundwood logs, and 3 % roundwood from branches (Thomas, 2018). The timbers in the Arthurstollen mine were used to plank the galleries and build working platforms.

In the Late Bronze Age Christian von Tusch-Werk mine at Hallstatt, only round logs seem to have been found; split timbers, boards and planks are not mentioned among the 899 finds investigated (Grabner, et al., 2015, 297). By contrast, boards represent a very high proportion (unfortunately not quantified more precisely) among the pit timbers from the Late Iron Age opencast gold mines of La Fagassière and Les Fouilloux in the French Limousin, where they were used for planking and the construction of working platforms (Cauuet, 2000). To conclude, the dominance of boards and planks among the mining timbers from Prigglitz could indicate that they were used to support the pit walls, as cladding for the waste heaps, or to construct scaffolds, working platforms or staircases.

In summary, fir wood was processed according to log diameter. Thin logs were split in various ways and mainly processed into slabs or half logs, while boards, planks or laths with relatively standardized cross-sectional dimensions were produced from logs with a diameter of >20 cm. For the latter, relatively fast-growing conifers with wide growth rings were used, while very slow-growing fir trees were used for the slabs. The only round log (Timber 03) from Prigglitz-Gasteil was also cut from a slow-growing fir. With a diameter of 12 cm and an age of 41 years, it was older than most stem logs from the Mitterberg mines (mostly 10–32, max. 54 years) and, with an average growth ring width of 1.2 mm, also had much narrower growth rings (cf. Thomas, 2018). One difference between Mitterberg and Prigglitz was that at Mitterberg, moderately to very fast-growing conifers were used to produce slabs (SH-T-1: maximum growth rates of 3–4 mm per year, SH-T-2: growth rates of mostly 4–5 mm; Thomas, 2018, 81f.), whereas at Prigglitz they were decidedly slow-growing (<1 mm per year).

In all the cases where the species could be identified, the mining timbers found in core KB01 at Prigglitz-Gasteil were made of fir; at least no other wood species were observed. Despite the small size of the sample, it is worth thinking about the reasons for this seemingly

Table 6

Priggitz-Gasteil. Description of the mining timbers from core KB01. Measurements in round brackets () – after freeze-drying; measurements in square brackets [] – estimated values. Abbreviations: L = length, rad = radial, rec. = recorded, T = thickness, tan = tangential (splitting), W = width. Table: uibk/P. Trebsche, BOKU/M. Grabner.

Timber no.	Stratigraphic unit	Find no.	Depth [m]	Orientation	Type	Splitting	Measures [cm]				Taxon	Bark preserved	Growth rings (GR)	
							diameter	L	W	T			No. of measured GR	Mean GR width [mm]
01	01–33	2547	20.48–20.60	inclined	split timber (slab)	rad	7 (6.5)	15.6	6.5	3.2	<i>Abies</i>	yes	45	0.6
02	01–33	2549	20.50–20.56	not doc.	split timber (slab)	rad	6	20.2	4.1	1.2	<i>Abies</i>	yes	25	0.4
03	01–35	2551	21.05–21.20	ca. 40°	round log (stem)	–	12 (9.4–10.0)	19.3	9.8		<i>Abies</i>	yes	41	1.2
04	01–38	2556	22.33–22.38		lighting taper?	rad	not rec.	7.4	1.1	0.5	<i>Abies</i>	no	4	2.3
05	01–41	2562	25.80–26.00	ca. 60°	split timber (board)	tan	not rec. (8.5)	14.8	7.7	2.5	conifer	no	not investigated	
06	01–41	2569	26.00–26.14	vertical	split timber (board)	tan	[>20]	13.2	6.5	2.0	conifer	no	not investigated	
07	01–41	2566	26.12–26.26	ca. 45°	split timber (halved log)	rad	5.0	14.0	5.0	3.0	conifer	no	not investigated	<<1
08	01–41	2570	26.22–26.30	horizontal, across Timber 09	split timber (slab)	tan	11.2	14.2	8.6	2.3	<i>Abies</i>	yes	39	0.6
09	01–41	2574	26.15–26.32	ca. 80°	split timber (slab)	tan	[>20]	21.0	11.6	2.4–3.7	<i>Abies</i>	yes	25	0.8
10	01–41	2571	26.00–26.12	ca. 60°	split timber (slab)	tan	[>10]	11.7	7.9	0.6–1.7	conifer	no	11	1.6
11	01–41	2573	26.00–26.12	vertical	split timber (plank)	tan + rad	[>20]	15.5	8.5	1.5–3.3	conifer	no	not investigated	
12	01–42	2579	26.45–26.65	ca. 60°	split timber (board)	tan	[>20]	10.0	6.0	1.6	<i>Abies</i>	no	10	1.4
13	01–43	2581	27.00–27.18	ca. 50°, directly above Timber 14	split timber (lath)	tan	[>30]	27.0	3.9	2.7	<i>Abies</i>	no	9	3.0
14	01–43	2582	27.00–27.24	ca. 40°, directly below Timber 13	split timber (board)	rad	[>40]	32.2	8.5	4.0	<i>Abies</i>	no	34	2.5
15	01–44	2589	29.52–29.56	horizontal	split timber (plank)	tan	[>30]	16.6	8.0	1.4–2.4	<i>Abies</i>	no	12	1.9
16	01–41	2568	26.00–26.10	vertical, above Timber 06	wood chip	–	not rec.	6.5	2.5	0.6	indet.	no	not investigated	
17	01–42	2580	26.63–26.68		lighting taper	rad	not rec.	8.0	1.1	0.8	indet.	no	not investigated	

Table 7

Prigglitz-Gasteil. Radiocarbon dating results (by wiggle-matching) for the mining timbers from core KB01. Table: uibk/P. Trebsche (after Trebsche and Weixelberger, 2022).

Timber no., growth ring (GR) no.	Calibrated date (1 σ ; 68.3 %)	Calibrated date (2 σ ; 95.4 %)	Peak	Index A_{comb}
Timber 01, GR 44	994–956 BCE	1010–931 BCE (83.4 %), 921–893 BCE (12.0 %)	980/975 BCE	69.6
Timber 03, GR 39	1046–1030 (11.3 %), 1021–970 (51.4 %), 952–943 BCE (5.6 %)	1077–932 BCE	1005 BCE	110.7
Timber 08, GR 37	973–960 (14.2 %), 933–905 BCE (54.0 %)	984–891 BCE	920 BCE	55.1
Timber 14, GR 34	1052–995 BCE	1096–986 BCE	1030 BCE	132.1
Timber 15, GR 11	1005–958 (47.4 %), 942–922 BCE (20.8 %)	1016–905 BCE	930 BCE	112.1

exclusive use of fir.

One of the biggest problems in the open pit mine of Prigglitz-Gasteil must have been water management, as the pit had to be kept free of rain, as well as from slope and spring water. The use of wooden water basins, pipes, or bailers is certainly conceivable. The properties of fir wood (see below) speak in favour of its use in an environment of changing humidity, as historical sources for wood use always mention fir as a better choice than spruce for this purpose (Fischer, 1690, Gayer, 1928, Hufnagl, 1920, König, 1956, Laris, 1910, Leonhardi, 1792).

At that time, a mixed forest of beech, spruce and fir thrived in the surroundings of the mining area. According to the pollen diagram (Fig. 4), beech was the dominant tree species, with values of between 20 and 30 % of the total pollen sum, followed by spruce, ranging between 10 and 25 %, whereas fir achieved only about 5 % (see below). Since both the above-mentioned conifer taxa are suitable for producing split timbers, it is not clear why the less frequent fir was used instead of the more readily available spruce. Inverted proportions of the two species are attested by the large numbers of charred conifer needles, which were identified in the archaeobotanical macro-remains from the settlement terraces T3 and T4 (Table 8): While fir (*Abies alba*) needles occur ubiquitously on both investigated terraces, spruce (*Picea abies*) needles are highly abundant in the sediments of T3, but entirely missing on T4 – currently an entirely spatial differentiation between the two terraces as has to be pointed out: Half of the stratigraphical units concerned are not yet assigned to chronological units as defined for this paper. Nevertheless, together with the preliminary results from diameter reconstruction,

Table 8

Abundance of conifer needles in the investigated contexts of Prigglitz-Gasteil, grouped per settlement/working terraces and archaeological phases. Round brackets () – uncertain identification (cf. *Picea abies*). Colours indicate chronological units as defined in Table 2. Table: OeAW-OeAI/A. G. Heiss. Data compiled from <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248287.s001> (Heiss, et al., 2021).

Archaeological phase	Terrace T3										Terrace T4								Total			
	T3-05 A	T3-07	T3-08 A	T3-08 B	T3-08 C	T3-08 D	T3-08 E	T3-08 F	T3-10	T3-11	T4-09	T4-11	T4-12	T4-13 A	T4-13 B	T4-13 C	T4-13 D	T4-13 E		T4-13 F	T4-13 G	T4-13 A–G
<i>Abies alba</i>	5	11	78	53	2	221	199	3	260	1	105	36	4	1	10	25	6	45	135	1	15	1,216
<i>Picea abies</i>	2	3	27	17	1	26	28	2	39	1	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	147
Pinaceae	-	-	-	-	-	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
<i>Pinus</i> sp.	-	-	-	1	-	3	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5
Total	7	14	105	71	3	255	227	5	299	2	106	37	4	1	10	25	6	45	135	1	15	1,373

such divergences strongly indicate a wide range of processes at Prigglitz-Gasteil which have gone unnoticed, especially when it comes to the differentiated use of branches/twigs and will certainly need further investigation.

Looking at other mining contexts, fir and spruce were both generally used for the same purposes. In the Bronze Age mines at Mitterberg, two-thirds of the pit timbers were made of spruce/larch and one-third were made of fir (Thomas, 2018). Among the Bronze Age mining timbers from the Christian-von-Tusch site at Hallstatt, fir and spruce were represented in roughly equal proportions (40 % and 39 %, respectively), followed by beech, maple, ash, and larch in much smaller percentages (Grabner, et al., 2015). In modern mining, *Picea abies* (spruce) timbers even have the reputation of “warning” the miners of their impending collapse by producing loud cracking noises well in advance (Grabner, et al., 2009, Lincke, 1921, see also personal communications as recorded in Lobisser, 2005). However, this property was probably not as crucial in an open-cast mine like Prigglitz-Gasteil, unlike the extensive underground mines of Hallstatt or the Mitterberg region, for example.

A preference for spruce can also be observed in the case of the split boards used to construct the sluice-boxes for wet processing at the Troiboden site at Mitterberg (Pichler, et al., 2018), where the resin of the spruce wood would have been advantageous in the humid environment.

In the light of these usage patterns, the predilection for fir at Prigglitz-Gasteil merits further investigation. First and foremost, more samples should be investigated to ensure that the current picture is not distorted by the small sample size. So far, however, the exclusive use of fir for mining timbers can probably be attributed to a purposeful selection of wood that was easy to split and suitable for use under periodically wet conditions.

6. Conclusions

According to the preliminary pollen study of local vegetation history, the Late Bronze Age mine of Prigglitz-Gasteil was surrounded by a mixed forest, mainly composed of beech, spruce, and fir, corresponding to the potential natural vegetation (PNV) model. Beech was predominant, but conifers – spruce in particular – gained in importance with increasing altitude. The first settlement activities including tillage were observed at the transition from the Early to the Middle Bronze Age. Forest clearings mainly affected beech, spruce, and fir. The largest decline in percentages was observable in spruce, suggesting that this conifer was the species most felled, although it is not recorded amongst the mining timbers. Over time, the clearings became so extensive that in some areas a secondary succession occurred, with pioneering species (e.g., willows) appearing in the final mining phase. These pioneering woods were then also increasingly used as fuel.

As regards the use of different taxa, wood from two contexts has been investigated so far. First, a small series of mining timbers was discovered

in the humid fill layers of the opencast copper-ore mine. All of them (where determinable) were made of fir. The high proportion of boards and planks indicated that they were used to support the pit walls, as cladding for the waste heaps, or to construct scaffolds, working platforms or staircases. Remarkably, spruce was not used to produce split timbers, although spruce was more prevalent in the forest than fir. Thus, the use of fir was definitely based on a purposeful selection that could have been influenced by its greater suitability for periodically wet environments, e.g., for constructions relating to the drainage of the opencast mine.

The second context investigated were the settlement terraces immediately next to the mine, where dwellings and bronze casting workshops were located. The charcoals from flotation samples did not indicate any selection among the available taxa, but rather reflected the “principle of least effort”, with all the accessible woody species around the settlement being gathered. Firewood was probably selected based on proximity and certain physical properties such as state of dryness/decomposition (which heavily influence smoke emission) rather than species. The composition of the charcoal samples showed a significant increase in pioneering taxa (*Populus* and *Salix*, *Corylus avellana*, *Sambucus*) over the course of time, at the expense of climax forest species and indifferent species. From this, a considerable human impact on the vegetation could be inferred in the latest phase of the mining settlement (second half of the 9th c. BCE).

Unfortunately, wooden remains from other use contexts have not yet been discovered at the site of Priggglitz-Gasteil. It would be interesting to know what types of wood were used for the construction of the dwellings and for firing the smelting furnaces, which would have consumed a good deal of firewood. So far, we have no information about the use of beech trunks (only thin branches were detected among the charcoal remains) or of spruce, which, according to the pollen profile, decreased during the Late Bronze Age.

To conclude, the investigated wood and charcoal finds indicated a systematic and selective use of the wood species occurring in the surrounding forest, ultimately leading to a secondary succession of the woodland. At the current stage of the investigations, there is no evidence for any scarcity or shortage in the wood supply.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Thorsten Jakobitsch: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Silvia Wiesinger:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andreas G. Heiss:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Felix Faltner:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Klaus Oeggel:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Michael Grabner:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Resources, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Peter Trebsche:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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